

GERMANY

UNIVERSITY OF COLOGNE

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The basis for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) at German universities is the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) issued in 2006. It defines forms of discrimination, explicitly including sexual harassment, and obliges higher education institutions (HEIs) to establish a complaints unit for any discrimination-related issues. However, the AGG only includes employees, not students. In addition to national legislation, HEIs have to comply with regional laws and can create their own regulations. At present, there are over 400 HEIs in Germany, and there are no systematic data available on how many have developed regulations on GBV (Kocher & Porsche 2015). According to a survey conducted among HEIs, 54% of participating HEIs had established a complaints unit for cases of discrimination according to the AGG by 2016 (Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes 2020).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Cologne has developed a strong policy base on issues of sexualised violence and other forms of GBV. In the past 16 years, three main policy documents have been produced: first, an early text on taking action against sexual harassment in 2006 that stipulated the obligation of the university to protect its members from discrimination, sexual harassment, and violence; second, the Guideline on Dealing with Sexualised Discrimination that was developed by the Gender Equality Officer and published in 2013, which described the purpose, scope, and principles of the policy, prevention measures, informal and formal complaint procedures, and the availability of support resources. And finally, the current comprehensive Guideline on Dealing with Discrimination, Sexualised Violence, and Bullying, which was published in 2019.

The Guideline was developed by the Vice Rectorate for Academic Careers and Equal Opportunities in 2018, which was passed by the Senate and published in February 2019. Its development responded to the need to address other cases of discrimination and bullying at the university. It was also the result of a sub-project of the audit 'Shaping Diversity', which was completed at the university in 2019. As in the case of the previous Guideline on Dealing with Sexualised Discrimination, this directive was developed by a continuous working group of stakeholders from different levels and sectors at the university, including student representatives.

The policy document is divided into eleven parts that describe the scope of the policy, define forms of discrimination, violence and bullying, state actions that are prohibited, outline the duties of the university's management and persons in leadership positions, describe methods of awareness-raising and prevention, explain the advisory and appeal procedures, informal (advice) and formal procedures (complaints), and set out possible sanctions. The document also explains data collection and when the policy comes into force. The document describes the procedures involved in formal and informal responses to incidents. In addition, it discusses various forms of awareness-raising activities, many of which have been implemented, although not yet evaluated.

URLs

- › Guideline on Dealing with Discrimination, Sexualised Violence, and Bullying: https://vielfalt.uni-koeln.de/fileadmin/home/bdahmen/PDFs/Englisch/Guideline_Anti-Discrimination_Barrierefrei.pdf

Entry into force: 2019

TRAINING

The Gender Equality Officer (GEO) and other professionals have been trained to address issues of sexual harassment. Awareness-raising and prevention measures related to training include the following:

- making the Guideline known to all members and associates of the University of Cologne (e.g. through the use of websites, posters, and regular video and social media campaigns);
- providing information to persons with supervisory, managerial, or training responsibilities;
- integrating the issue into in-house-training courses, in particular in courses for other counsellors, managers, and teachers.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The policy addresses the following **four** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, stalking, and online violence.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The policy addresses all **7Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnership and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: The policy addresses all target groups, academic staff, non-academic staff, students and 'other' identified groups. The policy also applies to guests, trainees, and persons employed in a training context.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The document mentions diversity and difference in general. It specifically mentions gender diversity and sexual orientation. Discrimination is defined as disparagement, contempt, disregard, exclusion, or violence against persons based on actual or attributed group-specific characteristics such as gender, sexual orientation/identity, origin, disability/illness, religion/belief, or age, or based on other individual differentiating characteristics (e.g. appearance, institutional

membership in an organisation). Persons may belong to several disadvantaged groups and find themselves in situations of multiple discrimination on more than one ground.

Specific vulnerable groups: The policy identifies one group that is particularly vulnerable to GBV, which is staff working on temporary contracts.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The main document states briefly in the preamble that ‘the university calls on all members and associates to assume responsibility for themselves and others, and promotes a culture of noticing and identifying discriminatory, encroaching, or violent behaviour’.

The role of the bystanders is further elaborated on a website which states: ‘The document suggests several ways for bystanders to support victims: by devoting basic attention to harassing behaviour; offering help if there are signs of sexual harassment; addressing sexual harassment in a place of study or a workplace; direct intervention during an incident; offering to accompany a harassed person who is seeking advice; offering support when the person concerned is defending himself/herself; being available as witnesses; or contacting the Risk Management Office of the University of Cologne (contact number 0221 470-2200) or the police (110).’

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. The number of cases, the results of institutional procedures, and the services provided to the victims and (alleged) perpetrators are monitored. All of the university’s official advisory and complaints offices collect data on the number of complaints lodged and on the types of discrimination reported, and these data are recorded in an anonymous format and in compliance with all data protection regulations. The data are checked by the Department for Gender & Diversity Management at the end of the year. This serves to ensure the quality of the advisory and support services and helps the university develop appropriate prevention services.

Evaluation: Yes. Guideline on Dealing with Discrimination, Sexualised Violence, and Bullying undergoes continuous development, including through external evaluations (e.g. Federal Anti-Discrimination Agency), and is currently under revision again.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The policy sets out two step-by-step procedures for reporting and investigating, one for violence among students and one for violence among staff members. The student vs student procedure defines: who to contact, how to report, responsible persons/units, and sanctions. The staff vs staff procedure defines: who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, responsible persons/units and sanctions

Student vs student

Who to contact: responsible persons and units:

- › the complainant’s superior

- › the Complaints Office for Employees according to the General Equal Treatment Act
- › the Human Resources Division in the case of (student) employees
- › the Suggestions and Complaints Office for students
- › the Student Affairs Division in the case of students
- › the university management

How to report: 'The purpose of the formal procedure is to inform the responsible body of the allegations and, where appropriate, to take further action against the accused person(s) or institution. This can be initiated by the person lodging the complaint or by a third party without prior informal proceedings.'

Sanctions: With regard to students and all those mentioned under Section 1 who are not employed at the University of Cologne, the following measures may be considered, depending on the seriousness of the offence:

- › issuing verbal/written instructions or a warning
- › banning the individual from using (certain) university facilities
- › banning individuals from one or more courses
- › a housing ban (e.g. partial or temporary)
- › criminal charges.

Staff vs staff

The information in this case is the same as for student vs student, except for the information on the following:

Description of the investigation: 'In the case of employees, the procedure shall be reviewed by the Human Resources Division, and in the case of students by the Student Affairs Division or by the Legal Department. The accused person is asked to comment on the complaint in person or in writing. The notified bodies shall document all hearings and the established facts and inform all parties of the result.'

Sanctions: 'The following sanctions may be imposed on employees of the University of Cologne, depending on the seriousness of the offence:

- › a disciplinary talk
- › issuing verbal/written instructions or warnings
- › banning an individual from using university facilities
- › a housing ban (e.g. partial or temporary)
- › issuing a written warning
- › the individual may be transferred out of or to another position at the university
- › withdrawal of a teaching assignment
- › initiation of disciplinary proceedings
- › termination with or without notice (for cause)
- › criminal charges'.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researchers Monica Perez and Friederike Kressner in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

